

Protein content

High-protein mutants in rice

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Rice is the main source of calories and protein for more than two thirds of the world's population. An increase in the protein content of rice would substantially improve the protein intake of rice consumers. Three of the most common locally grown rice varieties, Basmati 370, Jhona 349, and IR8, were subjected to (a) 20,30,40, or 50 kR gamma rays at 1,250 rad/min with a CO⁶⁰ source of IARI, Delhi, or (b) 0.5, 1, or 1.5% aqueous solutions of EMS or DES for 6 hours. From nearly 40,000 plants, 396 mutants were isolated in M2 and carried to M3 generation. Of these, 24 mutants exhibited enhanced seed protein content (see figures).

IR8 mutants IRm 1 to 12 have improved grain type and early maturity; IRm 13 is small grained; and IRm 14 to 17 are fine grained, early, and high yielding. The seed protein production of IRm 17 is the highest, followed by that of mutant numbers 16, 14, 15, 5, 12, and 2. IRm 16, 17, 14, and 15 are fine grained, early, and high yielding; however, they exhibit some degree of lodging under heavy fertilization. They represent the most promising mutants and donors for breeding an improved IR8 that has the ideal plant type visualized by earlier writers. The Jhona mutants Jm 12, 11, and 4 possess very high grain yield and seed protein production; Jm 4, a dwarf like Jm 11, also resists lodging. Bm 6 and Bm 7 represent the most promising mutants of Basmati. They are dwarf and high yielding, with tremendously enhanced grain and seed protein production, but have a slightly reduced grain fineness.

Among the improved mutants, IRm 14 to 17 of IR8, Bm 6 and 7 of Basmati, and Jm 12 of Jhona are the most reliable genotypes (as judged by number of

grains per panicle) for use in further breeding programs. However, while the grain fineness of most is improved, it is

reduced in the Basmati mutants. Also, the improved mutants Jm 4 and 11 have fewer grains per panicle than Jhona.

Grain yield and seed protein content of some high protein mutants of rice, Kurukshetra, India.

Total seed protein production of some high protein mutants of rice, Kurukshetra, India.